

MEANS AND METHODS OF TEACHING AND TRAINING IN FOOTBALL

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Annotation: This topic covers teaching tools and methods, as well as training approaches used in football. Various aspects of teaching playing technique are considered, such as passing, hitting, dribbling, as well as tactical aspects, including organizing the game in defense and attack. Training methods are aimed at developing the physical qualities of players, such as endurance, speed, strength and flexibility, as well as improving playing skills. Effective teaching and training methods are discussed, as well as training principles to maximize player development and prepare them for success on the football field.

Keywords: Football, training, training, means, methods, playing technique, game tactics, physical training, exercises, training process.

The main means of teaching and training football players are physical exercise, hygiene factors and natural forces.

The formation and improvement of skills and abilities occurs mainly through the systematic implementation of physical exercises. They are diverse, and their choice is dictated by the tasks that are set in the process of learning and training. Physical exercise helps improve coordination of movements, increase strength, speed, endurance and agility. At the same time, the activity of the cardiovascular, respiratory and other body systems is improved and, consequently, athletic performance increases and the recovery process after exercise is accelerated. All exercises used in training football players can be divided into three groups:

- 1) competitive,
- 2) special preparatory,
- 3) general training.

Competitive exercises are integral motor actions or their combination that make up the subject of the game of football and are performed in full accordance with the rules of football competitions. Special - preparatory exercises include elements of competitive actions and their variants.

The composition of specially preparatory exercises is decisively determined by the specifics of the game of football.

General preparatory exercises are aimed primarily at the general training of a football player. With the help of general preparatory exercises, you can effectively solve the problems of comprehensive physical education and selectively influence the development of the basic physical qualities, motor skills and abilities of a football player.

All exercises used in training a football player can be divided into main and auxiliary. The main exercises include.

- a) exercises for general and special development of motor qualities.
- b) exercises for teaching and improving ball handling technique
- c) exercises for learning and improving tactics, combinations and game systems.

Auxiliary exercises include:

a) general developmental exercises that contribute to the formation of new systems of conditioned reflexes that expand the functionality of the body;

b) special exercises that, in the structure of movements, correspond or are close to various parts of a motor skill.

c) exercises from other sports that contribute to the formation of motor skills and expansion of the functional capabilities of the body.

Natural forces of nature and hygienic factors contribute to a better effect of exercises and other means on the body of those involved. And, of course, the correct alternation of stress and rest, timely nutrition, sleep patterns, occupational and household hygiene play an important role.

The methods of teaching and training football players are diverse and play an important role in the development of physical qualities, mastery of motor skills and their improvement, cultivation of will and moral education. They are selected depending on the tasks that need to be solved and the specific conditions of the educational and training process. The determining factors here are age, number, level of general and sports preparedness.

For each teacher, it is important not only to know these methods well and choose the right moment to use them, but, most importantly, to be able to use them correctly or in practice.

When constructing the education and training of football players, a variety of methods should be used, taking into account the characteristics of the students, the material being studied and the available opportunities. In training sessions, all methods are used in combination, although sometimes, depending on the tasks and specific conditions, one or another method is preferred.

The following groups of methods used in the process of training football players are known:

1. Visual methods: showing exercises on a diagram, layout, kilogram, viewing educational and official competitions.

2. Verbal methods: story, explanation, instruction, conversation, lectures, report.

3. Practical methods: the exercise method and its variants, the multiple method, variable repetition, interval gaming and competitive methods.

In addition to these basic methods, there are other methods for solving various training problems.

A large place in the learning process is occupied by the demonstration and explanation of the trainer himself.

The demonstration helps to get an accurate idea of the exercise. There are a number of requirements for the display. The technique being demonstrated must be clearly visible to all participants, so the coach chooses the most convenient place in relation to the group or team. The technique must be demonstrated slowly, clearly and expressively, focusing students' attention on the most important elements. So, when demonstrating a running kick to the ball, it is necessary to clearly highlight the moment of placing the supporting leg in relation to the ball. Shade the nature of the movement of the kicking leg in the ankle and knee joints. Despite the clearest demonstration, the complexity of the technique does not always allow those practicing to grasp the main thing.

Therefore, the mandatory display must be accompanied by an explanation or preceded by the display and explanations complement each other. What to give preference depends on the nature of the reception. Thus, teaching to see the ball with the outer part of the instep after you have already learned how to dribble the ball with the inside of the foot, it will be enough to limit yourself to demonstrations. When working with well-prepared football players and learning new techniques and tactical actions based on familiar material, you can only use an explanation. Demonstration material will also help significantly.

Using visual and verbal methods, only a general idea of the material being studied is created. To fully master the technique and tactics of the game, it is necessary to apply practical methods.

In each practical method of teaching and training, certain components or techniques are distinguished, the totality of which represents the method in its entirety. So, for example, the method of repeated repetition or movement or action includes the following techniques:

- a) the coach showing one or another action (for example, stopping) the ball, etc.
- b) encourage the football player to reproduce the actions shown, correcting possible errors on the fly as directed by the coach:
- c) the football player repeats the learned action until the formation of the corresponding automatic skill:
- d) Complicating the action, introducing new elements into it (for example, tactical combinations, etc.). It can be broken down into component elements and techniques and other methods.

According to the basic requirements for the method of teaching and training football players, these methods must:

- a) Correspond to the goals and objectives of training with the individual and age characteristics of football players:
- b) To ensure the activity of football players in the classroom, the conscious and lasting mastery of knowledge and skills of the game in promoting systematic and consistent training and learning to lead football players from easy to difficult from the known from simple to complex from general to specific, when the game is mastered, students develop a specific motor skill . Therefore, each technique is studied in accordance with the old formed motor skills. When learning the technique, the following sequence is observed:

- a) Familiarization with techniques
- b) learning the technique in difficult conditions
- c) improving reception in conditions close to gaming
- d) consolidation of the technique in the game.

Familiarization with the technique at this stage of training, students must correctly obtain a clear understanding of the technique.

At the same time, attention is paid to more important details of the movement. To create an idea of the reception, filmograms are used, diagrams, layouts, etc.

Before practicing, students must properly get a clear understanding of the technique. At the same time, attention is paid to the most important details of the movement. To create an idea of the reception, kilograms, layout diagrams, etc. are used.

Before students begin to perform the technique on their own, it is necessary to ensure that they reproduce it correctly. But even in the process of repeating what has already been

learned, it is necessary to systematically monitor the correct execution of the technique. By controlling the students, the trainer monitors all the details of execution. Every error noticed must be corrected immediately.

When studying techniques, you can use holistic and dissected teaching methods. With relatively simple actions, the technique is usually unlearned as a whole. For complex actions, take them in parts and then combine them into a whole.

With holistic training, one or another technique is performed immediately without breaking it down into elements. So, if a running kick is being learned, the coach does not first teach the running kick, then placing the supporting leg, and only then applying the mid-lift to the ball, but having shown the technique as a whole, he invites the students to immediately make a kick and then points out individual mistakes.

With a holistic method of teaching and training, the overall structure of the movement is preserved and the individual characteristics of the trainees are better used. This method is the main one when teaching technical techniques of the game.

With uncoupled training, one or another technique is mastered element by element, followed by their combination and mastery as a whole. However, when mastering elements separately, it is very difficult to reproduce the conditions in which the technique is performed; in general, the nature of performing the elements changes. Thus, when learning to hit a ball with a running kick, it is impossible to make a swing with the kicking leg while standing still, which would correspond in nature to a running swing. If you lose sight of this and learn the technique on the spot, it will be learned incorrectly and subsequently it will take a lot of time to learn it again. Therefore, the method of unbraced training should be used carefully and especially when learning very complex techniques, as well as to eliminate errors in performing a technique.

Learning a technique in complicated conditions at this stage of training, students master the correct structure of the movement.

In this case, it is necessary to strictly observe such a sequence in setting tasks before the student first needs to master the correct starting position, clarify how often the bodies participate in the movement, what is their direction and consistency. Then they achieve coordinated execution of movements according to the optimal amplitude of movement accuracy, and only after that requirements are made to the other parties to the reception. A prerequisite for this is the absence of any interference during the reception.

When studying technical techniques or tactical interactions, you can vary the execution conditions by changing the starting position, distance, direction when performing the technique, the number of interacting partners, etc. P.

During the learning process, students often make mistakes. When determining them, one should not be hasty. Depending on the nature of the error, the coach uses various techniques to direct it: emphasizing the technique, but sometimes repeating explanations, etc. At all stages of training and training, it is important to take an individual approach to students.

Improving a technique in conditions close to games After students have mastered a technical technique in strenuous conditions, this technique is improved in complicated conditions. In this case, multiple repetitions of the technique are used in a variety of combinations with other techniques, with different weather, etc. Thus, the improvement of a shot on goal is carried out by shots from various positions (volley, half-flight, in motion, with resistance) in various combinations with other techniques (stop - strike) dribbling mega-kick,

dribbling the ball - deceptive movements - kick) using special equipment. Conditions need to be made more difficult gradually. However, you should try to avoid monotony in the exercises and not overuse excessive repetition.

Consolidating a technique in the game A technique is finally consolidated during the process of performing it in the game. At this stage, educational games become of great importance. Before each educational game, the objectives must be clearly defined. At the same time, the coach focuses the students' attention not only on the correct execution of the technique, but also on its tactically correct use in a game setting.

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